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Efficiency in Insolvency Resolution Globally

It grew on average by 23.03% between 2013 and 2021 in the countries considered

"Ease of resolving insolvency" is an indicator used to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of a country's legal and regulatory system in resolving insolvency cases. This indicator measures various aspects of the insolvency process, such as the length of time it takes to resolve an insolvency case, from the start of proceedings to final resolution, and the associated cost, including legal and administration fees. The percentage of debt recovery by creditors is also assessed, i.e. the value that creditors manage to recover compared to the original value of the debt. Furthermore, the indicator examines the quality of the legal and regulatory system, evaluating the rules and institutions that govern insolvency procedures, the effectiveness of the courts, the transparency and predictability of the process, and the ability to rehabilitate businesses. The "Ease of resolving insolvency" indicator is often used in global reports on the ease of doing business, such as the World Bank's "Doing Business" report. A high score on this indicator suggests that the country has a more efficient and less costly system for resolving insolvencies, which can foster a more stable and attractive economic environment for investment.

Source: World Bank

Link: <https://archive.doingbusiness.org/en/data/exploretopics/resolving-insolvency>

Insolvency Resolution Efficiency Globally in 2021. The "Ease of resolving insolvency" indicator provides a detailed overview of the effectiveness of global legal and regulatory systems in managing insolvency cases. The 2022 data shows significant differences between countries, reflecting the varied capabilities of national legal systems to address insolvency resolution efficiently and effectively. At the top of the ranking we find Finland with a score of 92.7, followed by the United States with 90.5 and Japan with 90.2. These countries boast robust legal systems, which ensure relatively quick insolvency processes, low costs and high recovery rates for creditors. In particular, Finland's high ranking can be attributed to its efficient legal structure, transparency and predictability of legal procedures, as well as the effectiveness of specialized courts. The United States, with a slightly lower score, nevertheless displays a robust system, supported by a long tradition of well-established bankruptcy laws and a well-developed legal infrastructure that facilitates the rehabilitation of insolvent businesses. Nordic countries such as Norway (85.4) and Denmark (85.1) and those in Central and Eastern Europe, including Germany (89.8) and the Netherlands (84.4), maintain high scores thanks to legal systems well-regulated institutions that promote the quick and cost-effective resolution of insolvency cases. The presence of Slovenia (84.4) and Belgium (84.1) among the top places highlights how even small-medium sized countries can excel in this area. In contrast, countries such as Brazil (50.4), Greece (53.1) and Argentina (40) highlight significant weaknesses in their insolvency resolution systems. These lower scores indicate lengthy and expensive processes, often

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resulting in very low recovery rates for creditors. Bureaucratic complexity, slow legal procedures and lack of transparency are common factors contributing to these outcomes. It is interesting to note that large emerging economies such as China (62.1) and India (62) have mediocre scores. These countries, despite their economic size, have yet to develop more efficient and transparent systems for managing insolvency cases. In China, the lack of full implementation of legal reforms and political influence in insolvency processes can complicate the situation. In India, although there have been recent improvements thanks to the new bankruptcy law, full efficiency of the system has yet to be achieved. Developing countries such as Pakistan (59), Kenya (62.4) and Rwanda (57.2) show variable results, reflecting the heterogeneity of legal reforms and institutional capacities in these contexts. In Africa, emerging economies face significant challenges in improving the predictability and effectiveness of their insolvency proceedings, often hampered by inadequate legal infrastructure and limited resources. At the bottom of the ranking we find countries such as Angola, Cape Verde, Laos and Saudi Arabia, with a score of zero. These findings point to serious gaps in insolvency resolution systems, which can be attributed to a lack of adequate laws, institutional inefficiencies, corruption and political instability. In such contexts, insolvency resolution is often impractical, discouraging investment and limiting economic growth. Another interesting aspect is the relatively low ranking of countries such as Luxembourg (45.5) and Switzerland (62.6), which despite being known for their economic and financial stability, do not excel in insolvency resolution. This could be due to complex legal procedures or a lack of recent reforms in their legal systems. Overall, 2022 data on global insolvency resolution efficiency highlights the importance of a well-functioning legal system to support economic stability and investor confidence. Countries with high scores tend to have more dynamic and resilient economies, capable of managing business crises in a way that minimizes the economic impact and maximizes creditor recovery. In contrast, countries with low scores face greater economic difficulties and risk seeing capital flight and reduced investment due to a lack of confidence in the legal system's ability to effectively manage insolvencies. To improve their positioning, countries should invest in legal reforms that simplify insolvency procedures, reduce costs and improve the transparency and predictability of the process. Furthermore, it is crucial to promote the independence and efficiency of courts, as well as adequately train judges and other legal practitioners. Sharing best practices between countries with successful systems and developing ones could accelerate global progress in this area crucial to economic health and financial stability.

Insolvency Resolution Efficiency at a Global Level between 2013 and 2021. The analysis of data relating to the efficiency of insolvency resolution at a global level between 2013 and 2021 reveals a varied evolution in the performance of insolvency cases different countries. Finland, which recorded an efficiency of 95.1% in 2013, saw a slight decrease in 2021, falling to 92.7%, with a negative percentage change of 2.52%. In contrast, the United States improved its efficiency, going from 86.5% to 90.5%, an increase of 4.62%. Japan, another country with a high initial efficiency (98.3%), suffered a notable decrease, standing at 90.2% in 2021, with a negative percentage change of 8.24%. Germany showed a significant improvement, going from 82.9% to 89.8%, an increase of 8.32%. Some countries experienced drastic reductions, such as Norway, which went from 96.2% to 85.4% (-11.23%), and the Netherlands, which saw a drop from 94.1% to 84.4% (-10.31%). In contrast, Slovenia recorded an impressive increase of 58.65%, rising from 53.2% to 84.4%. Other European countries such as Belgium recorded a decrease, with a variation of -10.53%, going from 94% to 84.1%. In Asia, South Korea saw a slight decline in efficiency, going from 86.8% to 82.9% (-4.49%), while Hong Kong saw a steeper decrease of 23.78 %, going from 86.2% to 65.7%. China, on the other hand, significantly improved its efficiency, going from 38.5% to 62.1% (+61.30%). Some countries showed extraordinary improvements, such as Thailand, which saw an increase of 68.79%, going from 45.5% to 76.8%, and Mauritius, which improved by 68.11%, rising from 43.9% to 73.8%. In Eastern

Europe, the Czech Republic saw a notable increase of 33.28%, rising from 60.1% to 80.1%. Other emerging countries have recorded significant improvements. For example, Poland went from 58.2% to 76.5% (+31.44%) and India saw an impressive increase of 119.08%, going from 28.3% to 62%. Brazil also recorded a substantial improvement, going from 17.7% to 50.4% (+184.75%), while Indonesia had a notable increase of 328.30%, going from 15.9% to 68.1%. Some African countries have shown astonishing progress. Rwanda, for example, went from 4.4% to 57.2% (+1200%), and Mozambique saw an increase of 184.52%, going from 16.8% to 47.8%. However, some African countries such as Botswana recorded a significant decline, going from 69% to 48.2% (-30.14%). Performance in Middle Eastern countries also varies considerably. Qatar saw a significant decrease of 35.81%, from 59.2% to 38%, while the United Arab Emirates improved by 54.55%, from 31.9% to 49.3%. In summary, the data shows a very heterogeneous global panorama in terms of efficiency in resolving insolvency cases. While some countries have made notable progress, others have suffered significant regressions. The most striking improvements were recorded in emerging and developing countries, highlighting significant efforts to improve their legal and economic infrastructure to better manage insolvencies. Conversely, some countries with initial high performance have seen declines that may indicate new challenges or emerging inefficiencies in their systems.

Conclusion. Considering the period between 2013 and 2021, the value of efficiency in insolvency resolution grew by 23.03%, going from an amount of 45.21 units up to a value of 55.63 units for the countries considered. However, there are countries in which the value of efficiency in insolvency resolution has grown much more than the average such as Zimbabwe with +2641.67%, Rwanda with +1,200.00%, Philippines with +788.71% , Kyrgyz Republic with +371.71%, Indonesia with +328.30%. There are also countries in which this value decreased significantly between 2013 and 2021, namely Singapore with -23.24%, Hong Kong with -23.78%, China with -26.8%, Tajikistan with -26.80%, Botswana with -30.14%, Qatar with -35.81%.

Declarations

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